

Nanomedicine Treatment Strategies That Exploit Unique Characteristics of Tumor Vasculature and Microenvironment

Alia Torres and Taha Tsouli Kamal, Medical Student at UM6SS Morocco; Joe F. Bolanos, MD; Kevin Morris, MD; Abilash Haridas, MD
Society for Brain Mapping and Therapeutics

Introduction: Nanomedicine is an advanced methodology and technology for cancer therapy that uses nanoscale molecules or particles to deliver anticancer compounds to targeted cancer cells or tissues. Investigation of tumor vasculature and their microenvironment has revealed evidence and insight into the architecture of tumor vasculature, formation and molecular regulation of tumor angiogenesis, characteristics and regulation of tumor blood flow, and the sometimes acidic and hypoxic tumor core.

Discussion

Nanomedicine makes use of tiny particles to target the microenvironment and the vasculature of tumors, increasing the accuracy of drug delivery and the effectiveness of cancer treatments. We reviewed some articles on PubMed with these keywords: nanomedicine, tumor, vascular, vasculature, transcytosis, nanotechnology, nano tubules.

Enhanced Permeability and Retention Effect

Tumor cells release VPF/VEGF, which promotes fluid buildup and vascular permeability. The EPR effect leads to macromolecule accumulation in tumors. Nanoparticles have passive tumor targeting. Nitric oxide-releasing agents can enhance drug delivery. VEGF inhibitors suppress the EPR effect. Strategies for improving drug delivery include micro/nanobubbles, ultrasound, and responsive nanomaterials targeting the TME. [3]

Aberrant Tumor Vasculature

Tumor blood vessels have a specific peptides known as vascular zip codes, that bind to organ-specific sites within these vessels. This promotes targeted nanomedicine delivery to the affected area. In a recent review, iRGDs was highlighted as an example of this vascular zip code. iRGDs contains the Arg-Gly-Asp sequence and has potential therapeutic applications, including transcytosis and activation of tumor-targeted properties. Also, iRGD, associated with contrast agents, helps early cancer diagnosis by selectively detecting cancer cells. [1]

Irregular Proteolytic Activities

Researchers have developed over 50 MMP inhibitors to reduce proteolysis within tumors. The "theranostic method" integrates targeted diagnosis and therapy for efficient diagnosis, drug administration, and treatment response tracking. Nanomedical approaches expedite treatment using proteolytic-activated imaging agents or prodrugs. A nano platform is sensitive to matrix metalloproteinase 2 in the tumor microenvironment and was created using dendrigraft poly-l-lysine and poly(ethylene glycol) poly(caprolactone) micelles, which enhances tumor drug penetration by overcoming physiological barriers [2].

Imaging of tumor vessel pericytes, basement membrane, and perivascular sleeves. (a,b). Confocal microscopic images showing α -smooth muscle actin-immunoreactive pericytes (white, arrowheads) that tightly envelop endothelial cells (green, CD31 immunoreactivity) of a normal vessel (a) but are loosely attached to blood vessels in Lewis lung carcinoma cells (b, green, CD31 immunoreactivity). (c) Confocal micrograph showing coverage of blood vessels in Lewis lung carcinoma by an abnormally loose, fragmented, and multi-layered basement membrane (white, arrowheads) stained for type IV collagen immunoreactivity. Endothelial cells are marked by CD31 immunofluorescence (green). (From McDonald, D.M., and Choyke, P.L., Nat Med, 9, 713–25, 2003. With permission.)

Heterogeneous Blood Flow and Circadian Rhythm

Tumor blood flow is inconsistent and vary between different parts. Angiotensin II can increase blood flow and improve circulation in obstructed vessels, enhancing drug delivery. Vascular disruptive agents like combretastatin A-4 can target blood vessels, causing stasis and collapse. Blood flow in tumor tissue is lower during the day, suggesting that chemotherapy and angiotensin II infusion at night can improve drug penetration and interaction with tumor cells, leading to better outcomes. [4]

Conclusion: Nanodrug development is a process that proceeds from design and construction of a nanoparticle in the laboratory, to in vitro testing, to in vivo testing in a relevant animal model, and finally to clinical trials. Understanding the unique characteristics of the tumor microenvironment is essential for formulating nanodrugs that will target tumor vasculature and tumor cells, spare normal tissues, and potentially lead to improved clinical outcomes in patients with cancer.

1 Zuo H. iRGD: A Promising Peptide for Cancer Imaging and a Potential Therapeutic Agent for Various Cancers. J Oncol. 2019 Jun 26;2019:9367845. doi: 10.1155/2019/9367845.

2 Cun X, Li M, Wang S, et al. A size switchable nanoplatform for targeting the tumor microenvironment and deep tumor penetration. *Nanoscale*. 2018;10(21):9935-9948. doi:10.1039/c8nr00640g

3 Duan L, Yang L, Jin J, Yang F, Liu D, Hu K, Wang Q, Yue Y, Gu N. Micro/nano-bubble-assisted ultrasound to enhance the EPR effect and potential theranostic applications. *Theranostics*. 2020 Jan 1;10(2):462-483. doi: 10.7150/thno.37593. PMID: 31903132; PMCID: PMC6929974.

4 Matsunaga T, Matsunaga N, Kusunose N, et al. Angiotensin-II regulates dosing time-dependent intratumoral accumulation of macromolecular drug formulations via 24-h blood pressure rhythm in tumor-bearing mice. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun*. 2018;498(1):86-91. doi:10.1016/i.bbrc.2017.11.162